

Coordination Complexes of Some Group (IV) Halides. Preparation and Infrared Spectra of the Complexes of Group(IV) Halides with 1-Methyl-2 pyrrolidinone and Biuret as Ligands

S. C. JAIN and G. S. RAO

Chemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay-85

Manuscript received 17 July 1975 ; accepted 13 September 1975

Coordination complexes resulting from the interaction of group(IV) halides, MX_4 (where $M = Ti, Sn$ or Zr and $X = Cl$ or Br) with 1-methyl-2 pyrrolidinone(L) and biuret (BT) as ligands have been prepared and characterized. The compounds have been examined spectrophotometrically in the infrared (i. r.) region $4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to establish the possible coordination sites. The analytical results indicate that with $TiCl_4$ the ligand 'L' forms both 1:1 and 1:2 adducts whereas with $SnCl_4$ and $ZrCl_4$ only 1:2 adducts are formed. In the case of the ligand BT only 1:1 adducts have been obtained in each case.

An attempt to brominate some of the tetrachloro-complexes such as $TiCl_4.L$, $TiCl_4.2L$ and $TiCl_4.BT$, by reacting with an excess of BBr_3 has resulted in the formation of interesting mixed halide complexes such as $TiCl_2Br_2.L.BBr_3$, $TiCl_2Br_2.2L.2BBr_3$, $TiCl_2Br_2.BT$ and tetrabromo-complex of the type $TiBr_4.2L.2BBr_3$.

THE reactions of group (IV) halides with various organic ligands have been the subject of numerous studies¹⁻⁴. However, very little work has been reported on their addition compounds with lactams. In a previous publication⁵ on the complexes of Co^{II} halides with pyrrolidinone (*o*-butyrolactam) on the basis of i. r. results it was concluded that the bonding resulted through the carbonyl group only, though both $\nu(C=O)$ and $\nu(N-H)$ displayed lowering on complexation. To avoid possible interaction of the N-H group with the halogen of the metal in the complexes^{6,7}, in the present study it was considered interesting to use 1-methyl-2 pyrrolidinone and determine the coordination site.

In earlier publications on the complexes of diamides⁸ and imides⁹ with group (IV) halides it was found that the C=O group was more basic than the amino or imino groups. To compare the ligating behaviour of diamides with diurea, in the present work biuret was considered as a potentially chelating ligand which can coordinate to metal atoms forming ring structures either through oxygen atoms or through nitrogen atoms.

Since metal bromides and bromo- complexes have been directly prepared from the corresponding chloro compounds by interaction with liquid BBr_3 ¹⁰, it was also considered worth while to brominate some of the complexes and examine the reaction products.

Experimental

The Lewis acids $TiCl_4$, $SnCl_4$ and $ZrCl_4$ were obtained from commercial source and purified by appropriate methods^{1,11,12}. High purity BBr_3 used in the present work was prepared in this Division¹³. The ligands 'L' and 'BT' were from Aldrich Chemical Inc.,

and Fluka respectively and were used as such without further purification. The reactions were performed in solutions in CCl_4 or CH_2Cl_2 . The solvents were treated with P_2O_5 and fractionally distilled before use. Since the Lewis acids and their complexes are very sensitive to atmospheric moisture all the experimental manipulations were carried out in rigorously dried apparatus and handled in a dry box continuously flushed with dry nitrogen. The proportion of the reactants taken and the time of interaction in each case are detailed below :

$TiCl_4.C_5H_9NO$: ligand 0.016 mole, $TiCl_4$ 0.018 mole and 25 ml CCl_4 , time 48 hours.
$TiCl_4.2C_5H_9NO$: ligand 0.031 mole, $TiCl_4$ 0.014 mole and 25 ml CCl_4 , time 48 hours.
$SnCl_4.2C_5H_9NO$: ligand 0.018 mole, $SnCl_4$ 0.017 mole and 25 ml CCl_4 , time 48 hours.
$ZrCl_4.2C_5H_9NO$: ligand 0.022 mole, $ZrCl_4$ 0.0082 mole and 20 ml CH_2Cl_2 , time 7 days.
$TiCl_4.Biuret$: ligand 0.011 mole $TiCl_4$ 0.033 mole and 25 ml CH_2Cl_2 , time 7 days.
$SnCl_4.Biuret$: ligand 0.015 mole, $SnCl_4$ 0.034 mole and 25 ml CH_2Cl_2 , time 7 days.

The reaction mixtures were stirred using magnetic stirring device in a closed system. In each case solid powdery products were obtained which were filtered, washed with the solvent and dried *in vacuo* for several hours at room temperature. Analytical results are given in Table I.

$TiCl_2Br_2.C_5H_9NO.BBr_3$; $TiCl_2Br_2.2C_5H_9NO.2BBr_3$; and $SnCl_2Br_2.2C_5H_9NO.2BBr_3$:

These mixed halide compounds were prepared by the interaction of $TiCl_4 \cdot C_5H_9NO$, $TiCl_4 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO$ and $SnCl_4 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO$ respectively with BBr_3 . Liquid BBr_3 was added drop by drop to about a gram of the compound in a flask under magnetic stirring till the evolution of BCl_3 had stopped and the BBr_3 added was enough to form a slurry with the product. After an over night reaction at room temperature the excess BBr_3 was pumped out.

$TiBr_4 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO \cdot 2BBr_3$: This compound was prepared by reacting the compound $TiCl_4 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO$ with an excess of BBr_3 and refluxing the reaction mixture for 4 hr. The refluxing was carried out under dry nitrogen atmosphere (for which the refluxing unit was connected to a nitrogen line).

$TiCl_2Br_2$. Biuret and $SnCl_2Br_2$. Biuret: These compounds were prepared starting with $TiCl_4$. Biuret and $SnCl_4$. Biuret respectively and reacting them with an excess of BBr_3 at room temperature. The excess BBr_3 was pumped out as in the previous cases.

Analytical procedure: Metals were determined gravimetrically as their oxides. Halogens were precipitated from the filtrates as silver halides and estimated gravimetrically. In the case of dichloro-dibromo complexes total halogens were precipitated and weighed as $AgCl$ and $AgBr$. The obtained mixed silver halide per gram of the complexes was found to correspond to the calculated values for the respective compound (Table 2). For the dichloro-dibromo complexes nitrogen was estimated by modified Kjeldahl's method¹⁴. Wherever possible boron was estimated as boric acid by titrating it with standard alkali solution in the presence of mannitol¹⁵. The analytical results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Infrared spectra: The i. r. spectra ($4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer Model 21, in Nujol mulls using $NaCl$ optics. The sample mounting operations were carried out in a glove box under dry nitrogen. The results are given in Tables 3 and 4.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF THE TETRACHLORO COMPLEXES.

Compounds	Colour	Melting Point °C	Metal % Calcd. Found	Helogen % Calcd. Found	Nature of adduct
$TiCl_4 \cdot C_5H_9NO$	Yellow	139-40	16.58 17.1	49.01 48.6	1 : 1
$TiCl_4 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO$	Yellow	190-92	12.35 11.9	36.54 36.3	1 : 2
$SnCl_4 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO$	White	150-52	25.86 25.8	30.89 30.9	1 : 2
$ZrCl_4 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO$	White	190 D	21.15 21.4	32.12 32.4	1 : 2
$TiCl_4 \cdot C_5H_8N_2O_2$	Yellow	300	16.36 16.5	48.42 47.8	1 : 1
$SnCl_4 \cdot C_5H_8N_2O_2$	White	300	32.65 32.9	38.91 38.5	1 : 1

C_5H_9NO = 1-methyl-2 pyrrolidinone

$C_5H_8N_2O_2$ = Biuret.

D = Decomposed.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF DICHLORO-DIBROMO COMPLEXES

Compounds	Colour	Melting Point °C	Metal % Calcd. Found	Nitrogen % Calcd. Found	Boron % Calcd. Found	Amount of $AgCl + AgBr/g$ compd. Calcd. gms Found
$TiCl_2Br_2 \cdot C_5H_9NO \cdot BBr_3$	Red	108-10	7.87 8.2	2.23 2.05	1.72 1.90	1.95 1.83
$SnCl_2Br_2 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO \cdot 2BBr_3$	Cream	~185 D	11.32 10.7	2.76 2.52	2.06 2.25	1.71 1.62
$TiCl_2Br_2 \cdot C_5H_8N_2O_2$	Brown red	>300	12.54 12.5	10.99 10.7	— —	1.57 1.46
$SnCl_2Br_2 \cdot C_5H_8N_2O_2$	Cream	>300	26.22 26.1	9.27 8.98	— —	1.46 1.57
$TiCl_2Br_2 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO \cdot 2BBr_3$	Red	130-33	4.89 5.0	2.86 2.42	2.23 2.10	1.83 1.71
$TiBr_4 \cdot 2C_5H_9NO \cdot 2BBr_3$	Red	120-22	4.49 3.8	2.63 2.24	2.03 2.13	1.76 1.72

C_5H_9NO = 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone

$C_5H_8N_2O_2$ = Biuret

D = Decomposed

TABLE 3—INFRARED SPECTRA (CM⁻¹) IN NUJOL MULLS

C ₅ H ₉ NO(L) neat	TiCl ₄ .2L	TiCl ₄ .2L	SnCl ₄ .2L	ZrCl ₄ .2L	TiBr ₃ Cl ₂ . L.BBr ₃	SnBr ₃ Cl ₂ . 2L.2BBr ₃	Band assignments (5,28)
1688 vs	1620 vs	1600 sb	1625 vs	1595 s	1640 s	1650 sb	ν (C=O)
1500 ms	1495 sh	1500 sh	1495 s	1500 s	1500 sh	1502 sh	CH ₂ Sciss
1450 ms	1470 s	1465 sh	1465 sb	1468 sb	1468 s	1468 sb	CH ₂ Sciss and Nujol
1440 sh	—	1440 s	1445 s	1440 s	1445 s	1440 sb	} CH ₂ Sciss
1428 s	1415 ms	1420 ms	1410 s	1410 sh	1410 s	1405 s	
1380 s	1375 s	1380 s	1375 s	1378 s	1380 s	1378	Nujol
1295 s	1350 s	1340 s	1340 s	1350 s	1300 m	1300 mb	} ν (C-N)
1260 s	1310 s	1315 s	1310 sh	1310 sh	1245 ms	1245 sb	
1225 w	1235 ms	1232 m	1260 m	1260 w	1210 sh	1210 sh	} ν (CH ₂ -N)
1165 m	1165 w	1160 w	1162 w	1160 w	1145 w	1142 m	
1065 w	—	1055 w	1060 w	1062 w	1080 m	1075 m	} (CH ₂) rocking.
1017 w	—	1010 w	1010 w	1012 w	1015 sh	1020 m	
978 m	—	970 wb	978 w	970 w	995 w	998 w	} ν (B-N)
—	—	—	—	—	775 ms	780 mb	

s=strong (28) K. Kurosaki, Nippon Kagaku Zasshi, 82, 1691 (1961); CA 58, 13312 d (1962)

m=medium

w=weak

sh=shoulder

b=broad

v=very

TABLE 4—INFRARED SPECTRA (CM⁻¹) IN NUJOL MULLS

Biuret (BT)	TiCl ₄ .BT	TiCl ₃ Br ₂ .BT	SnCl ₄ .BT	SnCl ₃ Br ₂ .BT	Band Assignments(21,22)
3340 s	3560 s	3560 s	3565 s	3570 s	ν (N-H)
3350 sb	3450 s	3450 s	3450 s	3455 s	
—	3300 sh	3285 sh	3300 m	3350 s	
1725 s	1690 sh	1690 sh	1695 sh	1695 sh	ν (C=O)
1700 s	1665 s	1670 s	1675 s	1680 s	
1590 s	1595 s	1595 s	1600 s	1600 s	δ (NH ₂)
1490 m	1530 sh	1530 sh	1500 sh	1500 sh	ν (C-N) + ν (C-NH ₂)
1460 s	1460 s	1460 s	1460 s	1460 s	Nujol.
1420 s	1435 s	1440 sh	1440 s	1440 s	ν (C-N)
1372 s	1372 s	1372 s	1375 ms	1375 s	Nujol.
1325 ms	1330 s	1335 s	1335 s	1338 s	δ (N-H)
1125 m	1185 wb	1250 w	1185 wb	1250 w	ν (C-N) out of phase + δ NH (imide type)
1075 m	1105 s	1105 s	1105 s	1110 s	δ (C-NH ₂) δ (C=O)
770 wb	758 s	758 m	762 s	765 m	
707 wb	745 sh	746 sh	755 ms	755 w	

s=strong

m=medium

w=weak

sh=shoulder

b=broad

Results and Discussion

Compound of MX₄ with 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone :

Lactams which are the cyclic counterparts of the open chain amides, can coordinate through one or both of the donor atoms. It is well known that the carbonyl stretching frequency ν (C=O) is lowered when the oxygen is involved in coordination^(8,9,12,16,17). A coordination through oxygen in the ligand L should result in the

lowering of the ν (C=O) and at the same time increasing ν (C-N), due to the electron shifts as shown in (a).

If coordination takes place through the nitrogen (b)

then decrease in $\nu(\text{C-N})$ would be observed while $\nu(\text{C=O})$ may either show an upward shift or may not be much effected. If both the oxygen and the nitrogen coordinate at the same time they can do so to two different metal atoms but are less likely to chelate.

The infrared spectra results in Table 3 give a clear indication about the involvement of the C=O group in coordination. A lowering of the order of 60-90 cm^{-1} has been observed for $\nu(\text{C=O})$ in the case of tetrachloro-complexes. In the region usually assigned to $\nu(\text{C-N})$ three bands at 1295, 1260 and 1225 cm^{-1} for the free ligand are observed. In the case of tetrachloro complexes four bands i. e. 1350, 1310, 1260 and 1235 cm^{-1} are observed. Since the nitrogen atom in the ligand molecule is bonded to three structurally different carbon atoms, on coordination one would expect non-uniform effect on different $\nu(\text{C-N})$ bands. In fact the one with carbonyl carbon will be more electronically sensitive to the coordination. It seems that the band at 1295 cm^{-1} for the free ligand shifts upwards and splits into two bands, one at 1350 cm^{-1} and the other at 1310 cm^{-1} as a result of lattice effect¹⁸ usually observed in solid state. The two bands at 1260 and 1225 cm^{-1} are little effected as a result of coordination.

It is interesting to note that TiCl_4 forms two types of adducts, 1:1 and 1:2 with the ligand. The formation of the 1:2 adduct can be explained on the basis of its octahedral structure where the two ligand molecules are coordinated either in *cis* or in *trans* positions. The 1:1 adduct can have several possibilities: (i) If the ligand acts as a monodentate, the titanium would exhibit a coordination number of five in a monomeric state, or coordination number of six in dimeric state involving chlorine bridging. (ii) If the ligand acts as a bidentate then it can either chelate on the same metal atom forming a strained four-membered ring or it can bridge two metal atoms imparting a polymeric structure to the product. Since the i. r. spectrum of the 1:1 adduct is identical to that of the 1:2 adduct, it seems that in the 1:1 adduct also the ligand is monodentate, coordinating through the carbonyl oxygen alone. In view of the fact that 1:1 adducts like $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CN}^{10}$, $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot (\text{CH}_2)_4\text{S}^{19}$ and $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CON}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2^{16}$ were shown to be dimeric in structure with chlorine bridging, in the present case also the compound $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{NO}$ is assumed to be dimeric in solid state. Molecular weight of these adducts could not be determined due to their strong dissociation in solution.

Compounds $\text{TiCl}_2\text{Br}_2 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{NO}$, $\text{SnCl}_2\text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{NO}$, 2BBr_3 and $\text{TiBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{NO} \cdot 2\text{BBr}_3$: Brown et al⁶ have prepared actinide bromo complexes by use of liquid BBr_3 . In the present study an attempt has been made to brominate the representative tetrachloro complexes of titanium and tin. It is interesting to note that two of the four chlorines easily get replaced by bromines when interacted with an excess of liquid BBr_3 at room temperature. In addition to partial bromination of the metal chloride in the complex, BBr_3

itself gets coordinated to the available nitrogen on the ligand molecule. It has, however, been possible to obtain tetrabromo compound $\text{TiBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{L} \cdot 2\text{BBr}_3$ by refluxing $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{L}$ with excess BBr_3 .

The i. r. spectra of these chloro-bromo complexes still show a lowering of 48 and 38 cm^{-1} in the $\nu(\text{C=O})$ (Table 3) but the magnitude is less compared to that of 68 and 63 cm^{-1} observed for the respective parent compounds. In the $\nu(\text{C-N})$ region the new bands at 1350 and 1340 cm^{-1} for the parent compounds are absent and three bands in the region 1300, 1245 and 1210 cm^{-1} appear for the mixed halide complexes. On comparison with the respective $\nu(\text{C-N})$ band for the free ligand one finds that the band at 1260 cm^{-1} is shifted to 1245 cm^{-1} and that at 1225 cm^{-1} to 1210 cm^{-1} . The band at 1295 cm^{-1} for the free ligand remains almost unaffected and appears at 1330 cm^{-1} for the complexes. Thus the changes in i. r. spectra in the $\nu(\text{C=O})$ and $\nu(\text{C-N})$ regions suggest bonding through both the donor atoms. A new band near 775-790 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the mixed halide complexes can be assigned to B-N stretching frequency as neither the free ligand nor the parent tetrachloro complexes display any band in this region. Taylor and Cluff²⁰ have also reported boron-nitrogen dative bond for amine-borane complexes in the region 800-650 cm^{-1} .

Compounds of MX_4 with biuret

Biuret is known to form the following two types of chelate rings:

The oxygen-bonded structure (i) and N-bonded structure (ii) have been confirmed by X-ray analysis of bis (biuret) Cu(II) chloride²¹ and potassium bis (biuret) Cu(II) tetrahydrate²². These two linkage isomers can be differentiated by i. r. spectroscopy.

The i. r. spectral studies of biuret complexes have been carried out earlier by Aida *et al*^{23,24} and McLellan and Melson²⁵ where band assignments have been made on an empirical basis but Kedzia *et al*²⁶ have made theoretical calculations based on vibrational analysis. The i. r. spectra of the free ligand as well as its complexes in the present study (Table 4) display two $\nu(\text{C=O})$ bands. For biuret these bands appear at 1725 and 1700 cm^{-1} while for the complexes they are shifted to 1690 and 1665 cm^{-1} , strongly suggesting the involvement of the carbonyl groups in coordination. Appearance of two $\nu(\text{C=O})$ bands in biuret compounds is not surprising as the $\nu(\text{C=O})$ in compounds containing CO.NH.CO group have been reported to give rise to two $\nu(\text{C=O})$ bands²⁷.

It is interesting to note that as expected the (N-H) bands at 3540 and 3350 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{C-N})$ bands at 1490 and 1420 cm^{-1} for biuret undergo positive shifts to

3560, 3450 and 3300 cm^{-1} for $\nu(\text{N-H})$ and to 1530 and 1440 cm^{-1} for $\nu(\text{C-N})$ respectively as a result of complex formation. Biuret in the solid state contains hydrogen-bonding between the NH_2 and CO groups. Hydrogen bonding usually results in a lowering of the $\nu(\text{N-H})$. Thus it appears that H-bonding present in the ligand is reduced on coordination. The insoluble nature of these compounds in inert organic solvent restrict our study to i. r. only. But the fact that the bromination of the TiCl_4 .Biuret and SnCl_4 .Biuret with BBR_3 only resulted in the replacement of two chlorines giving MCl_2Br_2 .Biuret where BBR_3 itself did not coordinate to any of the available nitrogens, shows that the biuret complex molecules are in highly associated form.

In view of the fact that these compounds neither decompose nor melt upto 300° and are insoluble in most of the inert solvents one cannot rule out the possibility of a polymeric structure of the type:

where $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups are still the coordination sites.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. M.D. Karkhanavala, Head, Chemistry Division for encouragement during the course of this work. Thanks are also due to Drs. H. S. Ahuja and M. S. Gill for helpful discussions.

References

- H. J. EMELEUS and G. S. RAO, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4245.
- G. S. RAO, *Z. anorg. U. allegem. Chem.*, 1960, 304, 176.
- G. S. RAO, *Z. anorg. U. allegem. Chem.*, 1960, 304, 351.
- I. R. BETTIE, *Quart. Rev.*, 1963, 42, 382.
- O. BOHUNOVSKY, S. C. JAIN and R. RIVEST, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1969, 47, 1689.
- J. CHATT, L. A. DUNKANSON and L. M. VENENZL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2712.
- A. NAKAHARA, Y. SAITO and KUROYA., *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1952, 25, 331.
- S. C. JAIN and R. RIVEST., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2787.
- S. C. JAIN and R. RIVEST., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, 31, 399.
- D. BROWN, J. HILL and C. E. F. RICKARD., *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1970, 476.
- S. C. JAIN and R. RIVEST., *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1963, 41, 2130.
- S. C. JAIN and R. RIVEST., *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1962, 40, 2243.
- H. S. AHUJA, I. A. KHAN, P. P. KUNTE and G. S. RAO, B. A. R. C. report 1972, No. 1-174.
- SCATT, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis," Van-Nostrand, 1960, p 634.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis," Longmans, 3rd Ed. 1961, p 252.
- S. C. JAIN and R. RIVEST., *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, 42, 1079.
- S. C. JAIN and R. RIVEST., *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1967, 45, 139.
- S. C. JAIN., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, 35, 505.
- H. S. AHUJA, S. C. JAIN and R. RIVEST., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 2459.
- R. C. TAYLOR and C. L. CLUFF, *Nature*, 1958, 182, 390.
- H. C. FREEMAN, J. E. W. L. SMITH and J. C. TAYLOR, *Nature*, 1959, 184, 707.
- M. NARDELLI, G. FAYA and G. GIRALDI., *Acta. Cryst.*, 1963, 16, 343.
- K. AIDA, Y. MUSYA and S. KINUMAKI., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 1268.
- K. AIDA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, 23, 155.
- A. W. MC LELLAN and G. A. MELSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1967, 137
- B. B. KEZIA, P. X. ARMENDAREZ and K. NAKAMOTO., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 849.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1954, p.190.